

EXTRACTION OF WOOD FIBRES FROM POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARD (WET PROCESS)

PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET

Contributing to the EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating post-consumer fibreboard into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

PROCESS

Dieffenbacher's wet process uses steam to release fibres from post-consumer fibreboard chips. A fast depressurisation separates and dries the fibres which makes them suitable for sifting to remove impurities and former coatings. The recovered fibres are then usable for new fibreboard production.

APPLICATIONS

The wet process can be integrated into:

- Medium and high-density fibreboard (MDF, HDF) production lines
- Wood fibre insulation board production lines

ACHIEVEMENTS

- Advanced to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6, converting around 25 tonnes of post-consumer fibreboard into high-quality recovered fibres comparable to virgin fibres.
- Tolerates contaminants (e.g. metals, stones, plastics and all kinds of coatings), which are subsequently removed to meet quality requirements.
- Low thermal and electrical energy demand improving economic performance.
- Available at industrial scale, with combinable units processing 1.5 and 4 tonnes per hour.

NEXT STEPS

- Test a wider range of input materials, aiming to enable the process to handle pre- and post-consumer fibreboard (MDF, HDF), laminate flooring and insulation products.
- Optimise operating settings to maximise fibre quality and impurity removal.
- Refine plant layout to support integration into industrial lines.

PARTNERS

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CONTACTS

DIEFFENBACHER GMBH MASCHINEN- UND ANLAGENBAU

Germany

MICHAEL RUPP

Head of Business Unit Recycling

[dieffenbacher.com](https://www.dieffenbacher.com)

michael.rupp@dieffenbacher.com

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Department of Forest Biomaterials and Technology - Division of Wood Science and Technology | Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

[slu.se](https://www.slu.se)

[More information:](#)

[EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

[.ecorefibre.eu](https://www.ecorefibre.eu)

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